

Flaws in EEG Alzheimer’s ML: Memorization, Lucky Folds, and Metric Misalignment

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Abstract

Reported EEG Alzheimer’s accuracy can be dominated by evaluation choices rather than model quality. Using OpenNeuro ds004504 (65 AD/CN subjects; DOI: 10.18112/openneuro.ds004504.v1.0.8), we show three evaluation traps that can inflate or destabilize results. **Trap 1: subject overlap enables memorization.** When train and test include the same subjects, fingerprinting (subject-ID classification) and AD/CN classification both reach near-ceiling epoch accuracy, consistent with subject memorization rather than disease learning. **Trap 2: lucky folds.** Under leakage-free, subject-disjoint Leave- P -Subjects-Out (LPSO), performance still depends strongly on which subjects are held out, making single-split results non-reproducible. **Trap 3: metric misalignment.** Epoch accuracy can disagree with subject-accuracy and can change model/hyperparameter rankings. We compute subject-accuracy as one decision per subject: label a subject AD if a majority of that subject’s test epochs are predicted AD (otherwise CN; $\tau = 0.5$). We recommend repeated subject-disjoint evaluations and reporting performance across many folds (median/IQR, or min/max). Importantly, there is a study scope here since the instability and quantization magnitudes reported here are demonstrated in a small-to-medium cohort setting ($N = 65$, primarily $P \in \{2, 6\}$). Similar effects can still arise in larger datasets when held-out cohorts are relatively small or non-representative, including cases where favorable folds are selectively reported. At a bare minimum, studies must disclose the held-out subject IDs per fold and report both epoch accuracy and subject-accuracy (subject-accuracy as primary).

1 Introduction

EEG has long been studied as a potential biomarker source for Alzheimer’s disease [9, 10], but reported machine-learning performance is highly sensitive to evaluation design [3, 4, 7]. We formalize three evaluation traps that can dominate reported accuracy. **Trap 1 (subject overlap \Rightarrow memorization):** if train and test contain epochs from the same subjects, models can exploit person-specific “fingerprints” and achieve near-ceiling accuracy without learning disease patterns that transfer to unseen subjects [5, 6]. **Trap 2 (small held-out cohorts \Rightarrow lucky folds):** even under leakage-free, subject-disjoint evaluation, measured performance can vary strongly with which subjects are held out for testing. Small test cohorts, a single split (or a small number of folds) is often not a reliable estimate of cross-subject performance. **Trap 3 (epoch–subject misalignment):** epoch accuracy can disagree with subject-accuracy, because subject predictions require one decision per subject. We compute subject-accuracy by aggregating a subject’s epoch predictions and predicting AD when a majority of that subject’s epochs are predicted as AD (equivalently, AD-ratio ≥ 0.5). Because epoch accuracy and subject-accuracy weight observations differently (epochs vs subjects), their divergence can increase under unequal epoch counts per subject. In this study, we quantify that divergence in a small to medium setting ($N = 65$, $P = 2, 6$). Recent work has scaled EEG-AD detection to over 2,000 subjects using subject-independent evaluation and majority voting for subject-level decisions [8]. In very large cohorts, these traps may appear with different magnitudes. How these effects scale in larger datasets remains an open empirical question.

We therefore propose a minimum reporting standard for subject-disjoint EEG claims: use the large held-out cohorts; when cohorts are small, use repeated subject-disjoint splits and report distributions (median/IQR or min/max) across many folds; report both epoch and subject-accuracy; and disclose held-out subject IDs per fold (or provide split manifests) to ensure results are reproducible and comparable.

Contributions.

- An auditable demonstration of all three traps on OpenNeuro ds004504 under subject-disjoint LPSO evaluation.
- A subject-accuracy decision rule based on majority vote over epochs (predict AD if at least half of a subject’s epochs are predicted AD; equivalently AD-ratio ≥ 0.5), used to compute fold-wise subject-accuracy.
- A reproducibility requirement: publish held-out subject IDs per fold (or split manifests) alongside performance reporting.

Roadmap: We first show subject-overlap memorization controls (Trap 1). We then quantify cohort sensitivity via lucky-fold tail behavior and a $P = 6$ vs. $P = 2$ stress test (Trap 2), followed by epoch-accuracy and subject-accuracy mismatch diagnostics (Trap 3), and we state the minimum reproducibility standard (split disclosure).

2 Dataset and Preprocessing

We utilize the OpenNeuro dataset ds004504, which contains resting-state EEG recordings collected for Alzheimer’s disease research [1, 15]. The first classification study on this dataset used leave-one-subject-out validation [2]; however, subject-independent evaluation is not consistently adopted in EEG classification studies more broadly [3, 4]. We use this dataset because it is widely used in the literature and publicly accessible, enabling a fully auditable evaluation.

Signal preprocessing and epoch-level feature preparation were implemented in Python with MNE-Python [16].

After quality control, the dataset includes 65 subjects (36 Alzheimer’s disease, 29 controls). After preprocessing and epoch rejection, the analysis uses 33,014 epochs (mean 508 ± 167 epochs per subject; range 185–845).

2.1 EEG Recording Parameters

Recordings are sampled at 500 Hz with a 19-channel 10–20 montage (Fp1, Fp2, F3, F4, C3, C4, P3, P4, O1, O2, F7, F8, T3, T4, T5, T6, Fz, Cz, Pz) in an eyes-closed resting-state condition. The dataset documentation describes a referential montage using Cz as the reference; recordings are approximately 5–21 minutes depending on the subject (controls approximately 12.5–16.5 min; AD approximately 5.1–21.3 min). Data descriptor: 10.3390/data8060095.

2.1.1 Filtering and Referencing

Signals are high-pass filtered at 0.5 Hz to remove slow drift and low-pass filtered at 30 Hz to define the analysis band used for feature extraction. Because the analysis band is capped at 30 Hz, mains interference at 50/60 Hz is excluded by design and we do not apply a separate notch filter in the reported results.

2.1.2 Epoching

Signals are segmented into 3-second epochs (1500 samples at 500 Hz). We use a sliding window of 0.5 as a fraction of the window size, corresponding to 50% overlap (stride = 1.5 seconds).

2.1.3 Artifact Detection and Rejection

Epoch rejection is automated and deterministic. We reject epochs using amplitude/flatness thresholds (reject = $600 \mu\text{V}$; flat = $0.3 \mu\text{V}$) and respect dataset annotations when available. No manual visual inspection steps are used in this analysis.

2.1.4 PSD Feature Extraction

Power spectral density (PSD) features are computed using Welch’s method [12, 16] over 0.5–30 Hz. We compute per-channel total band power and per-channel relative band power within canonical frequency bands (Delta 0.5–4 Hz, Theta 4–8 Hz, Alpha 8–12 Hz, Beta 12–30 Hz). Relative-power features are normalized by total band power within each epoch.

2.2 Feature Engineering

We extract 95 features per epoch:

Spectral Features (76). Relative band power in four bands (Delta, Theta, Alpha, Beta) for each of 19 channels, yielding $4 \times 19 = 76$ features per epoch.

Global Power Features (19). Total band power per channel, yielding 19 features per epoch.

2.3 Feature transformations

After feature extraction, pipelines differ only in the feature transformation stage. In the PCA pipeline, we first apply Z-score standardization and then perform PCA retaining 95% of explained variance. Z-scoring is used because PCA is variance-driven; without standardization, components can be dominated by a small number of high-variance features. A quick sanity check confirmed that omitting Z-scoring yields an unrealistically small number of retained components and weaker accuracy, consistent with standard PCA behavior.

In the F-test feature pipeline, we apply univariate F-test feature selection with family-wise error control at $\alpha = 0.05$. To prevent leakage, all transformations are fit using training data only and then applied unchanged to the corresponding test data: the PCA pipeline applies the fitted scaler and PCA transform, and the F-test pipeline applies the selected feature set. In subject-overlap settings there is a single train/test split, but the same rule applies (fit on train only, apply to test); in LPSO settings this is done independently within each fold.

3 Metrics and Decision Unit

EEG classifiers are often trained on short windows (epochs), while final decisions are made per subject. This section defines the metrics used in this paper and how they are summarized.

3.1 Epoch accuracy and subject-accuracy

Terminology and metrics (single reference point). Subject-disjoint (subject-independent) means no subject appears in both train and test within a fold; in this paper it is implemented with Leave- P -Subjects-Out (LPSO), where P is the number of held-out test subjects per fold. Subject-overlap (subject-dependent) allows train/test subject overlap and is used only as a memorization control, not as cross-subject evaluation. Fingerprinting is subject-ID classification from EEG epochs and is used here as a memorization diagnostic under subject-overlap [5, 6, 17]. A fold is one held-out LPSO cohort; a run is one evaluated configuration on one fold (fold \times model \times hyperparameter setting).

Subject-accuracy is the primary metric: each held-out subject gets one vote via AD-ratio thresholding ($\tau = 0.5$). Epoch accuracy is diagnostic: it is computed over test epochs and implicitly weights subjects by epoch count, so it can diverge from subject-accuracy. With LPSO, fold-wise subject-accuracy is quantized in steps of $1/P$ (for $P = 6$, $1/6 \approx 16.67\%$; for $P = 2$, $1/2 = 50\%$), so small- P results are interpreted as stability diagnostics rather than precise clinical performance. Unless otherwise stated, headline epoch-accuracy summaries use **Median(all runs)** (pooling folds and hyperparameter settings); full pooling details are provided in Appendix A.

3.2 Evaluation design: split strategies

We use two subject-disjoint LPSO fold strategies throughout the paper, summarized in Table 1. **Systematic-12** uses a deterministic `systematic_ordered` generator with `wrap_around`: with $N = 65$ and $P = 6, 7$

Table 1: Experiments and split designs used in this paper. IDs use paper-facing aliases (F-test = univariate F-test, SD = subject-disjoint, SO = subject-overlap). All experiments use the same cohort ($N = 65$). Random-50 has 50 folds, Systematic-12 has 12 folds, and subject-overlap controls use 10 random 80/20 splits. In the $P = 2$ Random-50 setting, full subject coverage is not enforced ($N_{\text{test}} = 49$).

Experiment ID	Feature pipeline	Split type	Fold strategy	P	Folds	N_{test}
F-test_SD_6_Random	F-test	Subject-disjoint	Random-50	6	50	65
PCA_SD_6_Random	PCA	Subject-disjoint	Random-50	6	50	65
F-test_SD_2_Random	F-test	Subject-disjoint	Random-50	2	50	49
PCA_SD_2_Random	PCA	Subject-disjoint	Random-50	2	50	49
F-test_SD_6_Uniform	F-test	Subject-disjoint	Systematic-12	6	12	65
PCA_SD_6_Uniform	PCA	Subject-disjoint	Systematic-12	6	12	65
F-test_SO_C	F-test	Subject-overlap	Random 80/20	–	10	65
F-test_SO_F	F-test	Subject-overlap	Random 80/20	–	10	65
PCA_SO_C	PCA	Subject-overlap	Random 80/20	–	10	65
PCA_SO_F	PCA	Subject-overlap	Random 80/20	–	10	65

subjects fill double test-fold slots (all 65 subjects appear in at least one test fold). **Random-50** draws P subjects uniformly at random per fold; it does not enforce full cohort coverage, so some subjects may never be drawn ($P = 2$ covers only 49 of 65 subjects). Random-50 is intentional as a stress-test of cohort sensitivity rather than a population-representative benchmark.

4 Experiments & Results

4.1 Experimental setup

We evaluate two feature pipelines (PCA and univariate F-test feature selection) and four models (KNN, SVM, XGBoost, MLP) with a fixed 3-setting hyperparameter grid per model (12 model \times HP configurations per fold; full grid in Appendix C). Implementations use scikit-learn for KNN/SVM/MLP [13] and XGBoost for gradient-boosted trees [14]. We use subject-overlap splits only as memorization controls and subject-disjoint LPSO for the main evaluation. Split strategies (Systematic-12 and Random-50 at $P \in \{6, 2\}$) and experiment IDs are defined in Section 3.2 and Table 1.

Boxplot convention. In all boxplots, each model is represented by the hyperparameter configuration with the highest median accuracy across folds (i.e., the best-average HP setting per model). This means each box summarizes the distribution of fold-level results for that model’s best-performing configuration, not a pooled or random selection. Also consider the fact that each fold is represented by a dot on the boxplots.

4.2 Trap 1: Subject overlap enables memorization

We perform subject-dependent evaluations using 10 random 80/20 subject-overlap splits, where each subject’s epochs are independently split 80/20 so epochs from the same subject appear in both training and test. All 65 subjects contribute to each split’s test set. High accuracy here may reflect subject memorization, not disease generalization. Variation across the 10 splits was negligible, confirming that the memorization signal is stable regardless of which epochs are held out. These subject-overlap splits are used only as memorization controls and are not reported as deployable cross-subject performance.

Figure 1: **Trap 1 diagnostic control (subject-dependent): fingerprinting by epoch accuracy.** Left: PCA features; right: F-test features. The x-axis lists models (MLP, XGBoost, SVM, KNN) and the y-axis is epoch-accuracy (0 to 1). Boxplots summarize the distribution across hyperparameter configurations; overlaid points are individual runs from the same subject-dependent split.

Figure 2: **Trap 1 diagnostic control (subject-dependent): disease classification by epoch accuracy.** Same layout as Figure 1: left: PCA; right: F-test. Models on the x-axis, epoch accuracy on the y-axis, boxplots/points over hyperparameter configurations.

Figure 3: Trap 1 diagnostic (PCA features): fingerprinting mirrors overlap-based disease accuracy, and subject-disjoint evaluation produces a collapse in median accuracy. Left panel: epoch-accuracy distributions for fingerprinting and disease classification, both evaluated under subject-overlap splits (PCA pipeline; 10 random 80/20 splits). Right panel: epoch-accuracy distributions for disease classification under subject-overlap vs subject-disjoint LPSO ($P = 6$, Random-50; 50 folds). Models (MLP, XGBoost, SVM, KNN) are on the x-axis; epoch accuracy (0 to 1) on the y-axis; the dotted horizontal line marks 50% chance. In the left panel, fingerprinting and overlap-based disease accuracy follow similar distributions, consistent with both tasks exploiting subject-specific epoch structure. In the right panel, enforcing subject-disjoint evaluation reduces median accuracy toward chance and widens fold-to-fold variability, indicating that a portion of the overlap-based disease signal reflected subject-identity leakage rather than generalizable disease features.

Across models and feature pipelines, fingerprinting reaches near-ceiling epoch accuracy under subject-overlap splits, showing that subject identity is strongly recoverable when train and test contain epochs from the same individuals [5, 6, 17]. Under the same overlap-prone evaluation, AD/CN classification is also very high. The key point is that this does not imply strong cross-subject disease generalization. Instead, subject overlap makes both tasks easier because models can exploit stable person-specific EEG structure [3, 7]. We therefore treat subject-overlap disease results as memorization controls, not as deployable performance estimates. This makes subject-disjoint evaluation necessary because it removes identity leakage that overlap-based splits hide. However, it is not sufficient by itself. When the held-out cohort is small, fold-to-fold variation can become large enough that a single split looks unusually strong or weak by chance. This motivates Trap 2.

4.3 Trap 2: Lucky folds under subject-disjoint evaluation

Even when subject-disjoint evaluation is enforced, a single fold can yield a non-representative performance estimate if the held-out cohort is small. Under LPSO, the measured accuracy for a given fold reflects the specific subjects assigned to the held-out cohort. Some held-out cohorts may over-represent subjects who are easier or harder to classify, producing unusually high or low values by chance rather than by model quality. Unlike Trap 1, this instability persists even when subject-disjointness is enforced and identity leakage is removed. We use epoch accuracy as a cohort-sensitivity diagnostic throughout this section because it is high-resolution and consistently recorded across all experiments. Under Random-50 resampling, the run-level distribution (fold \times hyperparameter configuration) exhibits wider tails and greater spread, revealing that fold-to-fold variability is substantial even after leakage is eliminated. Random-50 makes the lucky-fold trap directly observable by exposing fold-to-fold variation across many held-out cohorts. A baseline comparison of fold-strategy effects (Systematic-12 vs Random-50 at $P = 6$) is provided in Appendix E (Figure 10); a concrete illustrative example of single-fold spread for one model/pipeline setting is provided in Table 6 of the same appendix.

4.3.1 Stress test: $P = 6$ vs $P = 2$ under Random-50

To isolate the effect of hold-out cohort size, we compare Random-50 at $P = 6$ and $P = 2$ under the same pipeline and model families, holding the fold-generation strategy constant. The hypothesis is direct: smaller P means fewer subjects per held-out cohort, reducing the averaging effect and increasing the chance that any single cohort draw falls far above or below the cross-subject mean.

Note on subject-accuracy at small P . When $P = 2$, fold-wise subject-accuracy is restricted to $\{0\%, 50\%, 100\%\}$; these values should be interpreted as instability diagnostics, not as precise performance estimates.

Figure 4: **Trap 2 cohort-sensitivity stress test.** Random-50 LPSO; epoch accuracy; $P = 6$ (left column) vs $P = 2$ (right column). Top row: PCA features; bottom row: F-test features. The four models (MLP, XGBoost, SVM, KNN) appear on the x-axis; epoch accuracy (0–1) on the y-axis. For each model the single best-performing hyperparameter configuration (selected by highest median across 50 folds) is shown; each point is one fold ($n = 50$). The red dashed line marks chance (0.5). Because the same hyperparameter configuration is used in both the $P = 6$ and $P = 2$ panels, hyperparameter variation cannot explain the observed IQR inflation because the sole variable is cohort size P .

Table 2: **Trap 2: IQR inflation under cohort-size reduction (Random-50; best model per feature; $n = 50$ folds each).** The model and hyperparameter configuration are locked within each feature block (P is the sole variable). Medians shift only modestly (+5 pp) while the IQR nearly doubles in both feature sets, confirming that the variance inflation is driven by cohort size rather than model or hyperparameter differences. Both selected models are also the best performers in Figure 4 ensuring authenticity.

Feature	P	Model (HP)	Median	IQR (pp)	Min – Max	IQR Ratio
F-test	$P = 6$	MLP (layers=[100])	72.0%	12.9	52.6% – 89.7%	—
F-test	$P = 2$	MLP (layers=[100])	77.0%	21.5	39.8% – 98.3%	1.7×
PCA	$P = 6$	SVM (kernel=rbf)	56.5%	8.1	38.5% – 74.3%	—
PCA	$P = 2$	SVM (kernel=rbf)	59.7%	15.9	28.8% – 84.0%	2.0×

Figure 4 and Table 2 together show that reducing the hold-out cohort size from $P = 6$ to $P = 2$ substantially increases fold-to-fold variability. Critically, the table locks each feature block to the same model and hyperparameter configuration at both P values. For F-test, the best model is MLP (layers=[100]); for PCA, it is SVM (kernel=rbf). Therefore, hyperparameter variation cannot explain the IQR inflation. For F-test (MLP), the IQR increases from 12.9 pp to 21.5 pp (1.7×); for PCA (SVM) it increases from 8.1 pp to 15.9 pp (2.0×).

In both cases the median shifts only modestly (+5 pp), while the IQR nearly doubles. This is a consistent pattern with increased cohort-composition luck rather than a systematic shift in model quality. This instability is distinct from Trap 1: here, evaluation is fully subject-disjoint and identity leakage is removed. The source of variability is instead the composition of the held-out cohort itself. When only $P = 2$ subjects are held out per fold, the measured accuracy is sensitive to whether those two subjects

happen to be consistently easy or consistently difficult to classify, independent of the model’s generalizing ability. The IQR of 12.4 pp for F-test and 6.9 pp for PCA at $P = 6$ confirms that meaningful fold-to-fold variation remains even at the larger hold-out size and the lucky-fold effect is not unique to the smallest P .¹ This means that a single fold, even under leakage-free subject-disjoint evaluation, is not a reliable estimate of cross-subject performance. The result depends partly on which cohort was drawn, not only on the model. Some folds yield results that would appear publishable in isolation, while adjacent folds from the same experiment yield near-chance values; reporting only the best fold or a single fold without identifying which subjects were held out therefore provides an incomplete and potentially optimistic picture of model behavior.

The practical consequence for benchmarking is that model comparisons based on a single or small number of folds can be driven by cohort luck rather than genuine differences in cross-subject generalization. The recommended mitigation is repeated subject-disjoint resampling over many folds and reporting distributions rather than point estimates, especially for small-to-medium test cohorts. At minimum, reports should state the subject-disjoint protocol, hold-out cohort size (P), number of repeated folds, and median and IQR (with min/max) across folds, together with disclosure of held-out subject IDs per fold so that results are reproducible.

4.4 Trap 3: Metric misalignment (epoch vs subject-accuracy)

4.4.1 Primary results: subject-accuracy (P=6)

Subject-accuracy is computed fold-wise under LPSO with $P = 6$ by thresholding each held-out subject’s AD-ratio at $\tau = 0.5$ (majority vote): predict AD if at least half of that subject’s test epochs are predicted AD.

Table 3: **Subject-accuracy summary (P=6; Random-50; Mode 1)**. Median and IQR (percentage points) of *fold-wise subject-accuracy* for each model \times pipeline under LPSO Random-50 with $P = 6$ and Mode 1 (hyperparameters selected by epoch accuracy, then evaluated at the subject-accuracy unit). Computed from `raw_info/paper_subject_eval_outputs_03-02-26/fold_subject_accuracy.csv` ($n_{\text{folds}} = 50$). With $P = 6$, subject-accuracy is quantized in steps of $1/6 \approx 16.67\%$.

Model	PCA median	PCA IQR (pp)	F-test median	F-test IQR (pp)
MLP	50.00%	0.00	83.33%	33.33
XGBoost	50.00%	0.00	83.33%	16.67
SVM	50.00%	0.00	83.33%	16.67
KNN	50.00%	16.67	83.33%	33.33

¹These IQR values reflect the pooling convention **Median(all runs)** (pooled across folds and hyperparameter settings); the locked best-HP row values from Table 2 are 12.9 pp and 8.1 pp respectively.

Figure 5: Primary (Trap 3): subject-independent LPSO ($P=6$) subject-accuracy distributions. 2×2 grid: top row PCA, bottom row univariate F-test; left column Systematic-12, right column Random-50. In each panel the y-axis is fold-wise subject-accuracy (0 to 6). Boxplots summarize the distribution across folds; points are individual folds. Because $P = 6$, subject-accuracy is quantized in steps of $1/6 \approx 16.67\%$.

For subject-accuracy, univariate F-test consistently dominates PCA across models, and Random-50 reveals meaningful fold-to-fold variability driven by which subjects are held out. Because $P = 6$ implies coarse quantization, we treat these as the correct *unit*, not as high-precision clinical estimates. However, models are typically tuned and compared using epoch accuracy. We therefore test whether epoch accuracy is a reliable proxy for subject-accuracy and whether it selects the same best model.

4.4.2 Mismatch diagnostics

Trap 2 is about *which* subjects are held out. Changing the held-out cohort changes the measured performance. Trap 3 is about *how* we aggregate predictions for the same held-out subjects. Even within a fixed fold, epoch accuracy and subject-accuracy can disagree because epoch accuracy reweights subjects by their epoch count while subject-accuracy gives each subject one equal vote. Throughout this section

we define $\Delta = \text{subject-accuracy} - \text{epoch accuracy}$; $\Delta < 0$ indicates that epoch accuracy overestimates subject-accuracy.

Mechanism (one fold). Figure 6 shows the single fold with the maximum epoch–subject discrepancy ($\Delta = -24.5$ pp) across all F-test $P = 6$ folds (F-test; MLP; Systematic-12), selected to make the mismatch mechanism maximally visible: two large, correctly classified subjects dominate the epoch count while four subjects are misclassified. This is a worst-case illustration; typical folds show smaller gaps (see Figure 7 for the full distribution).

Figure 6: **Mismatch mechanism (Trap 3): worst-case fold by $|\Delta|$ (F-test; MLP; Systematic-12; $P = 6$).** Left: epoch votes per held-out subject. Bar height = epoch count; solid fill = correctly classified; hatched = misclassified. Vote ratio annotated above each bar. Epoch counts vary across subjects. Subjects with more epochs have an outsized effect on epoch accuracy. Right: resulting aggregate metrics side-by-side. Epoch accuracy (57.9%) is driven upward by the large, correctly classified subjects; subject-accuracy (33.3%, 2/6 correct) gives each subject one equal vote. The yellow band shows the gap between epoch accuracy and subject-accuracy. This fold has the largest $|\Delta|$ across all F-test $P = 6$ folds and is shown to make the mechanism maximally visible. Typical folds show smaller discrepancies.

Figure 7: **Mismatch prevalence (Trap 3): fold-wise epoch vs subject-accuracy scatter ($P=6$; Random-50; $\tau = 0.5$)**. Each point is one fold (hyperparameters selected by epoch accuracy; Mode 1). The x-axis is fold-wise epoch accuracy; the y-axis is fold-wise subject-accuracy ($\Delta = y - x$; $\Delta < 0$ below the diagonal means epoch overestimates); the diagonal $y = x$ marks equality. Horizontal bands along the y-axis reflect the quantization of subject-accuracy at $P = 6$ (steps of $1/6 \approx 16.67$ pp); this is a property of the metric, not a plotting artifact. Points deviate from the diagonal across all 50 folds, showing that epoch-accuracy improvements do not map reliably to subject-accuracy gains.

Figure 8: **Mismatch at model level (Trap 3): mean epoch vs mean subject-accuracy per model \times HP configuration ($P = 6$; Random-50; $\tau = 0.5$)**. Each point is one model \times HP configuration; the x-coordinate is its mean epoch accuracy across all 50 folds and the y-coordinate is its mean subject-accuracy across the same 50 folds. The hyperparameter configuration is held fixed within each point. Circles = Random-50; squares = Systematic-12. Points that fall below the $y = x$ diagonal have a higher mean epoch accuracy than mean subject-accuracy ($\Delta < 0$). The spread around the diagonal shows that epoch rankings can diverge substantially from subject-accuracy rankings.

Figure 7 demonstrates that the mismatch observed in the worst-case fold is not an outlier. Across all 50 folds, points deviate substantially from the $y = x$ diagonal, showing that epoch accuracy is a noisy proxy for subject-accuracy. This pattern persists at the model \times HP level as well: Figure 8 confirms that aggregated epoch rankings can diverge significantly from subject-accuracy rankings even after pooling across folds. These rank reversals are not marginal. In the F-test pipeline (Random-50; $P = 6$), KNN with $n_neighbors=1$ ranks 10th by mean epoch accuracy (64.8%) but 1st by mean subject-accuracy (84.3%); the top-ranked configuration by epoch accuracy — MLP $layers=[100]$ at 71.4% — ranks only 4th by subject-accuracy (81.0%). A researcher, or an algorithms objective function, optimizing or reporting

by epoch accuracy alone would select the wrong model for subject-accuracy. Epoch-accuracy gains are therefore best treated as a diagnostic rather than headline evidence for model comparison.

Secondary diagnostics. Per-subject heterogeneity plots (which are not fold-wise subject-accuracy) are provided in Appendix G. Additional biomarker and threshold sensitivity analyses are in the Appendix as supplementary material.

Minimum reproducibility standard (split disclosure). Subject-independent performance is cohort-sensitive (Trap 2) and epoch accuracy can mis-rank subject-accuracy (Trap 3). Subject-independent results must therefore disclose held-out subject IDs per fold ideally by providing machine-readable split manifests. For this manuscript, split manifests for the main paper settings are bundled in `manifests.zip` (including wide and long CSV variants). See Appendix B (Appendix B) for the format and an excerpt.

4.5 Summary

Table 4 summarizes key performance metrics across all experimental conditions.

Table 4: **Performance summary with subject-accuracy as the primary subject-independent metric.** Subject-independent subject-accuracy is computed fold-wise via AD-ratio thresholding at $\tau = 0.5$ and reported under Mode 1. Epoch-accuracy headline values use the convention Median(all runs) and are included here as a diagnostic for fold instability (Trap 2) and epoch–subject mismatch (Trap 3), not as a primary model-selection metric.

Validation Method	Leakage	Primary: median subject-accuracy (Mode 1)	Diagnostic: median epoch acc	Interpretation
Subject-dependent 80/20 (fingerprinting)	Yes	–	97.6% (IQR 0.2 pp)	Subject memorization control
Subject-dependent 80/20 (disease)	Yes	–	97.7% (IQR 2.1 pp)	Inflated by subject overlap
LPSO Random-50 ($P = 6$; F-test; e.g., MLP)	No	83.33% (IQR 33.33 pp)	69.5% (IQR 12.4 pp)	Subject-independent (primary: subject-accuracy)
LPSO Random-50 ($P = 6$; PCA; e.g., KNN)	No	50.00% (IQR 16.67 pp)	53.2% (IQR 6.9 pp)	Near-baseline at subject level
LPSO Random-50 ($P = 2$; F-test; e.g., MLP)	No	100.00% (IQR 50.00 pp)	76.6% (IQR 22.0 pp)	Highly unstable; heavily quantized

5 Discussion

Three evaluation design choices conspire to inflate reported EEG classification accuracy. First, when train and test share subjects, models can exploit person-specific structure rather than learning disease patterns that transfer to unseen individuals (Trap 1). Second, even under subject-disjoint evaluation, performance depends heavily on which subjects are held out, creating large fold-to-fold variability that invites cherry-picking (Trap 2). Third, the metric typically reported (epoch accuracy) can differ from subject-accuracy, leading to model mis-rankings and incomplete knowledge of true generalization (Trap 3). Together, these traps mean that reported single-split epoch accuracy is a poor proxy for clinical utility.

The core insight is that evaluation choices can drive accuracy more than model quality. This is not unique to EEG, but the field’s reliance on epoch-accuracy aggregation, small held-out cohorts, and split non-disclosure has allowed these traps to remain largely hidden [4, 3]. Most published EEG Alzheimer’s studies do not quantify fold variability, do not report subject-accuracy, and do not disclose held-out subject

IDs [3]. As a result, it is impossible for readers to assess whether reported numbers reflect genuine disease signal or lucky cohort draws.

5.1 Minimum reporting standard (and why we enforce split disclosure)

These traps imply a minimum reporting standard for subject-independent (subject-disjoint) EEG claims: (i) use subject-disjoint splits (avoids Trap 1); (ii) quantify cohort sensitivity with repeated resampling and report distributions, not single values (addresses Trap 2); (iii) report both epoch and subject-accuracy with explicit primary/diagnostic roles (addresses Trap 3); and (iv) publish held-out subject IDs per fold (or split manifests with seeds and fold-generation code) so results are reproducible and comparable (enables verification of Trap 2 claims and prevents ambiguous split reporting). This emphasis on transparent methodology and standardization is aligned with prior EEG-AD recommendations and leakage-focused evaluation work [11, 3, 7].

5.2 Limitations

This analysis uses one task (eyes-closed resting) and one cohort (AD vs control) from a single dataset (ds004504). Small held-out cohorts ($P = 6$ and especially $P = 2$) imply quantized subject-accuracy and limited precision; we therefore interpret subject-accuracy results as diagnostics of mismatch and instability rather than definitive clinical performance. Replication on additional datasets, paradigms, and acquisition protocols is needed to establish generality.

6 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that single-split epoch accuracy can be misaligned with subject-accuracy. Because subject overlap enables memorization (Trap 1), and independent cohorts exhibit large variance (Trap 2), the field cannot rely on epoch accuracy as the headline metric; instead, researchers should use subject-accuracy as the primary unit of evaluation (Trap 3). Taken together, these three failure modes make a direct case for mandatory split-manifest disclosures: without held-out subject IDs per fold, lucky-fold cherry-picking is undetectable, cohort sensitivity is invisible, and epoch–subject mismatch goes unreported. Adopting subject-disjoint evaluation, repeated resampling, and split disclosure as a minimum reporting standard would make EEG classification results reproducible, comparable, and trustworthy.

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A Reporting conventions and pooling over runs

All epoch-accuracy statistics reported in this manuscript are derived from the `test_accuracy` column in `raw_info/all_experiments_combined.csv`. Unless otherwise stated, subject-independent LPSO *epoch-accuracy* headline values follow **Median(all runs)**: the median and IQR are computed over *all* recorded runs for the relevant (experiment, model), pooling across folds *and* hyperparameter configurations.

Why this matters. Because **Median(all runs)** pools across both held-out cohort identity (folds) and hyperparameter settings, the resulting IQR reflects *both* cohort sensitivity and hyperparameter sensitivity.

Canonical source for pooled epoch-accuracy numbers. The canonical source for pooled epoch-accuracy summaries is the released repository artifacts under `raw_info/all_experiments_combined.csv` and `raw_info/accuracy_summary/`.

Subject-dependent (subject-overlap) controls. Subject-dependent controls (W_C, W_F) in this repository snapshot contain a single subject-overlap split; the reported IQR/min/max therefore reflect *hyperparameter* variation (three hyperparameter settings per model), not cross-validation variability. We include subject-dependent results only as leakage/memorization controls, not as estimates of subject-independent generalization.

Subject-accuracy summaries are different. Subject-accuracy is computed fold-wise from per-subject decisions (AD-ratio thresholded at $\tau = 0.5$). It should not be back-computed from epoch-accuracy pooled tables; subject-accuracy medians/IQRs must be derived from the per-subject evaluation artifacts.

B Split manifests (held-out subjects per fold)

To make subject-independent results reproducible and comparable, we provide machine-readable split manifests listing the **held-out test subject IDs per fold** for the LPSO settings used in this paper.

Manifest files. All manifest files are bundled in `manifests.zip`. This archive includes wide-format manifests (one row per fold with `subject_1..subject_P`) and long-format variants (one row per (fold, subject)). For readability, the long format is usually easiest to audit. Naming note: manuscript text uses **Systematic-12**, while the CSV strategy field may show **Uniform-12** for the same deterministic fold generator.

Table 5: **Excerpt of held-out subject IDs per fold (split disclosure).** Full fold manifests (all folds) are provided in `manifests.zip`.

Setting (excerpt)	Example held-out subject IDs
$P = 6$, Random-50 (fold 1)	10, 17, 30, 41, 44, 60
$P = 6$, Random-50 (fold 2)	10, 32, 36, 38, 43, 46
$P = 6$, Random-50 (fold 3)	11, 25, 30, 45, 57, 59
$P = 6$, Random-50 (fold 4)	11, 27, 32, 43, 52, 64
$P = 6$, Random-50 (fold 5)	11, 34, 35, 37, 47, 56
$P = 6$, Random-50 (fold 6)	12, 17, 33, 40, 53, 64
$P = 6$, Systematic-12 (fold 1)	10, 11, 12, 46, 47, 48
$P = 6$, Systematic-12 (fold 2)	13, 14, 15, 49, 50, 51
$P = 6$, Systematic-12 (fold 3)	16, 17, 18, 52, 53, 54
$P = 6$, Systematic-12 (fold 4)	19, 20, 21, 55, 56, 57
$P = 6$, Systematic-12 (fold 5)	1, 2, 3, 37, 38, 39
$P = 6$, Systematic-12 (fold 6)	22, 23, 24, 58, 59, 60

C Hyperparameter Grid

All experiments use a small, fixed hyperparameter grid shared across validation strategies.

- **KNN:** metric = euclidean; weights = uniform; $k \in \{1, 7, 15\}$.
- **SVM:** $C = 0.1$; $\gamma = \text{auto}$; kernel $\in \{\text{linear}, \text{rbf}, \text{poly}\}$.
- **MLP:** activation = tanh; $\alpha = 0.1$; hidden layer sizes $\in \{(100), (150, 50), (200, 100, 50)\}$.
- **XGBoost:** $n_estimators = 100$; $learning_rate = 0.2$; $subsample = 0.7$; $max_depth \in \{3, 6, 9\}$.

D Supplementary: Trap 1 diagnostic (both pipelines, 2×2 view)

Figure 3 in the main text shows the Trap 1 diagnostic for PCA features only. Figure 9 below extends the same comparison to both pipelines (PCA and F-test) in a 2×2 layout. The pattern is consistent across pipelines: fingerprinting mirrors overlap-based disease accuracy (left column), and subject-disjoint LPSO produces a drop in median accuracy and wider fold-to-fold spread (right column).

Figure 9: **Trap 1 diagnostic (both pipelines): fingerprinting vs overlap-based disease accuracy, and overlap vs subject-disjoint LPSO (2×2).** **Top row:** PCA pipeline. **Bottom row:** univariate F-test pipeline. **Left column:** fingerprinting vs disease classification, both under subject-overlap splits (10 random 80/20 splits). **Right column:** disease classification under subject-overlap vs subject-disjoint LPSO ($P = 6$, Random-50; 50 folds). Models (MLP, XGBoost, SVM, KNN) on the x-axis; epoch accuracy (0 to 1) on the y-axis; dotted line at 50% chance. Across both pipelines, fingerprinting and overlap-based disease accuracy follow similar distributions, and enforcing subject-disjoint evaluation reduces median accuracy and increases fold-to-fold variability.

E Supplementary: Trap 2 baseline fold-strategy diagnostic

This appendix provides two supporting diagnostics for Trap 2 that complement the $P = 6$ vs $P = 2$ stress test in the main text.

Fold strategy comparison: Systematic-12 vs Random-50 ($P = 6$)

Figure 10 shows epoch-accuracy distributions at $P = 6$ under both Systematic-12 and Random-50 fold strategies. Systematic-12 uses a deterministic, coverage-preserving generator (all 65 subjects appear in at least one test fold), while Random-50 draws hold-out cohorts uniformly at random. Comparing the

two strategies at the same P isolates fold-selection randomness from hold-out size effects. The Random-50 distributions consistently show wider spread, confirming that random cohort draws produce more variable results than the systematic design, even before reducing P .

Figure 10: **Supporting diagnostic (Trap 2): Systematic-12 vs Random-50 epoch-accuracy distributions ($P = 6$).** 2×2 grid: top row PCA, bottom row F-test; left column Systematic-12, right column Random-50. Models (MLP, XGBoost, SVM, KNN) on the x-axis; epoch accuracy (0 to 1) on the y-axis; dotted line at 50% chance. Boxplots show distributions across runs (fold \times hyperparameter configuration). Random-50 distributions are visibly wider than Systematic-12 at the same P , consistent with random cohort selection increasing fold-to-fold variability.

Illustrative single-fold spread: SVM + F-test, Random-50

Table 6 provides a concrete illustration of the fold-to-fold range for one model and pipeline (SVM + F-test; Random-50) at both $P = 6$ and $P = 2$. Each value is the best-HP epoch accuracy for one fold, sorted from lowest to highest. The table is an intuition aid, not a benchmark: it shows how much a single fold can differ from its neighbors purely due to which subjects were drawn.

F Supplementary: Subject-accuracy evaluation at $P = 2$

This appendix provides the subject-accuracy plots for the $P = 2$ stress-test setting. Because $P = 2$ implies subject-accuracy is restricted to $\{0\%, 50\%, 100\%\}$, these plots should be interpreted primarily as *diagnostics* of instability and quantization rather than as precise performance estimates.

Table 6: **Illustrative example (Trap 2): single-fold epoch-accuracy spread for SVM + F-test under Random-50.** Five representative folds (sorted low to high) at $P = 6$ and $P = 2$, using the best-HP accuracy per fold. $P = 6$ spans 50.1%–86.8% (range ≈ 37 pp); $P = 2$ spans 16.9%–92.6% (range ≈ 76 pp). This table is an intuition aid illustrating how cohort-composition luck scales with hold-out size; it is not a headline benchmark.

Setting (illustrative)	Fold A	Fold B	Fold C	Fold D	Fold E
SVM + F-test (Random-50; $P = 6$)	50.1%	66.3%	70.8%	77.1%	86.8%
SVM + F-test (Random-50; $P = 2$)	16.9%	59.7%	73.2%	76.6%	92.6%

Figure 11: **Subject-independent LPSO ($P=2$) subject-accuracy distributions (diagnostic; quantized).** Same layout as Figure 5 but with $P = 2$, so fold-wise subject-accuracy can only be 0%, 50%, or 100%.

Figure 12: **Epoch vs subject-accuracy mismatch scatter ($P=2$; diagnostic; quantized).** Same definition as Figure 7, but with $P = 2$, so the y-axis takes only three discrete values. This highlights that epoch accuracy can vary continuously while subject-accuracy changes in large steps when few subjects are held out.

G Secondary diagnostic: per-subject heterogeneity (not subject-accuracy)

This section is a *descriptive* stability diagnostic and is **not** a headline performance claim. Unlike fold-wise subject-accuracy (Primary), these summaries aggregate outcomes over many fold×model combinations and do not correspond to a single per-subject decision rule per fold. They are included to show between-subject heterogeneity (“easy” vs “hard” subjects) under different pipelines.

Calculation details and supporting per-subject summaries are derived from released per-subject prediction artifacts in this repository, primarily `raw_info/paper_subject_eval_outputs_03-02-26/per_subject_fold_predictions.csv` and `raw_info/paper_subject_eval_outputs_03-02-26/fold_subject_accuracy.csv`.

Key references: per-subject prediction CSVs and fold-level subject-accuracy CSVs in `raw_info/paper_subject_eval_outputs_03-02-26/`.

Where a derived per-model per-subject table is not directly vendored in this repository snapshot, we treat those breakdowns as supplementary and do not use them as main-paper headline tables.

Table 7: **Per-subject heterogeneity summary (secondary diagnostic; not subject-accuracy)**. For each experiment, we summarize (across subjects) two metrics computed from per-epoch predictions and aggregated over fold×model combinations. **Success rate**: for each subject, the percentage of fold×model combinations where that subject’s epoch accuracy exceeds 50%, then summarized across subjects. **Mean per-subject accuracy**: for each subject, the average epoch accuracy across fold×model combinations, then summarized across subjects. These diagnostics quantify heterogeneity and sensitivity to model/fold choice; they are not fold-wise subject-accuracy under AD-ratio thresholding.

Internal ID (legacy)	Success rate (median ± IQR)	Mean per-subject accuracy (median ± IQR)	Success rate min/max	Mean accuracy min/max
F-test_L_6_Random	98.53% ± 32.94 pp	74.65% ± 28.74 pp	0.00% / 100.00%	11.34% / 94.49%
PCA_L_6_Random	66.67% ± 50.00 pp	64.86% ± 46.41 pp	18.75% / 91.67%	18.20% / 89.20%
F-test_L_2_Random	100.00% ± 25.00 pp	75.28% ± 23.89 pp	0.00% / 100.00%	11.84% / 96.97%
PCA_L_2_Random	63.89% ± 43.75 pp	69.53% ± 45.94 pp	8.33% / 83.33%	13.97% / 82.51%

Figure 13: **Per-subject heterogeneity diagnostics for two pipelines (secondary; not subject-accuracy)**. The figure is a 2×2 grid: **columns** correspond to internal experiment IDs (left: F-test_L_6_Random; right: PCA_L_6_Random). **Top row**: per-subject success rate (% of fold×model combinations where that subject’s epoch accuracy exceeds 50%). **Bottom row**: per-subject mean accuracy averaged across fold×model combinations. The x-axis lists subjects sorted by success rate; the y-axis is success rate (top) or mean accuracy (bottom).

Figure 14: **Specific-model examples of per-subject stability (secondary; not subject-accuracy).** The figure contrasts two model configurations under the same experiment family F-test_L_6_Random (F-test; hyperparameters printed in the panel titles). **Top row** shows per-subject success rate; **bottom row** shows per-subject mean accuracy; subjects are sorted by success rate on the x-axis.

H Supplementary: Biomarker discovery (descriptive; not subject-level inference)

This appendix provides a descriptive biomarker summary for interpretability. These statistics are computed at the *epoch-feature* level and therefore treat epochs as samples; because epochs from the same subject are not independent, nominal p-values can be optimistic if interpreted as subject-level evidence. We therefore treat biomarker patterns as descriptive support (effect sizes and spatial patterns), not definitive subject-level inference.

Table 8: Top 10 EEG biomarkers for AD vs control classification. All features shown survive FDR correction ($q = 0.05$) in the underlying exploratory analysis. Ratio shows Control/AD for Alpha features (higher in controls) and AD/Control for Delta features (higher in AD).

Feature	Mean AD	Mean Control	Ratio	Cohen's d
O2 \times Alpha	0.0400	0.1064	2.66	0.797
T5 \times Alpha	0.0364	0.0916	2.51	0.715
O1 \times Alpha	0.0389	0.0951	2.45	0.704
O2 \times Delta	0.8888	0.8260	1.08	0.603
T6 \times Alpha	0.0379	0.0772	2.04	0.602
P3 \times Alpha	0.0278	0.0538	1.94	0.534
O1 \times Delta	0.8898	0.8378	1.06	0.511
T5 \times Delta	0.8896	0.8389	1.06	0.502
Pz \times Alpha	0.0259	0.0480	1.86	0.496
P4 \times Alpha	0.0285	0.0470	1.65	0.428

Spatial pattern summary. The strongest effects concentrate in posterior regions (occipital and temporal/parietal channels) and are dominated by alpha-band reductions. We also observe posterior delta elevations. These patterns are consistent with commonly reported AD-related changes in resting EEG [9, 18], but we treat them as interpretability support rather than headline inference.

I Supplementary: Threshold sensitivity analysis (non-nested; interpret cautiously)

Beyond the default $\tau = 0.5$ majority-vote decision rule for subject labeling, we performed an exploratory threshold sweep over $\tau \in [0.3, 0.7]$.

Method. For each held-out test subject, compute an AD-ratio: the fraction of that subject’s epochs predicted as AD. Threshold the AD-ratio at τ to produce a subject label, then compute fold-wise subject-accuracy.

Interpretation caveat. Selecting τ based on the same held-out fold predictions used for evaluation is optimistically biased unless threshold selection is nested (tuned on training/validation subjects and evaluated once on untouched test subjects). We therefore treat threshold plots as a *sensitivity analysis* and keep $\tau = 0.5$ as the default decision rule for the main paper.

J Extra: The Pipeline Needed for the Experiment (PySpark + Ray)

The experiments are powered by a distributed pipeline (PySpark + Ray) that ingests raw EEG files, applies deterministic preprocessing and epoching, computes spectral features, applies optional feature transforms (e.g., univariate F-test selection, PCA, scaling), and evaluates models under group-aware subject splits (LOSO/LPSO). The key design constraint is that any data-dependent step (e.g., feature selection) must be executed within each training fold to avoid leakage.

Why a distributed pipeline was necessary: scale of the experiment The leakage-free constraint—that every data-dependent transform must be *fitted independently on each fold’s training partition*—means no two runs can share a fitted transformer. With 4 models \times 3 hyperparameter settings = 12 configurations per fold, the total number of independent fit-transform-predict cycles across all 10 experiments is:

Experiment group	Pipelines	Folds	Configs/fold	Runs
Random-50, $P = 6$ (SD)	2	50	12	1,200
Random-50, $P = 2$ (SD)	2	50	12	1,200
Systematic-12, $P = 6$ (SD)	2	12	12	288
Subject-overlap (SO-C: disease)	2	10	12	240
Subject-overlap (SO-F: fingerprinting)	2	10	12	240
Total				3,168

Each of these 3,168 runs is a fully independent pipeline: the feature transformer (F-test selection or scaler+PCA) is fitted on the fold’s training epochs, applied to the test epochs, and then the model is trained and evaluated—none of these steps can be reused across runs. A sequential execution would have been impractical at this scale; the PySpark + Ray architecture allows fold-level and model-level parallelism to be exploited across workers, reducing wall-clock time to a manageable level while guaranteeing that the leakage-free constraint is preserved for every run.

Key Properties The pipeline is configured via versioned YAML and supports containerized execution. It can separate train/tune/test subject cohorts when needed, scales feature computation with PySpark, and caches intermediate artifacts (e.g., Parquet features with metadata) to make large resampling experiments practical.

Figure 15: **Distributed EEG analysis pipeline (PySpark + Ray) used to run large resampling experiments.** The diagram shows a containerized two-stage architecture. The **Spark container** performs deterministic preprocessing/epoching and scalable feature extraction (e.g., PSD-based bandpower features), then **saves** a fold-aware feature table with subject identifiers (e.g., as Parquet) for reuse. The **Ray container loads** these features and orchestrates group-aware subject splits (LOSO/LPSO), model training and hyperparameter evaluation, and per-fold testing, emitting per-fold test metrics and aggregated summaries. Arrows indicate the dataflow from raw EEG files → extracted features → fold-specific train/test evaluation, with the key constraint that any data-dependent transform (feature selection, scaling, PCA) is fit *within* each training fold to prevent leakage.

K Example Config

```
1 project:
2   name: F-test_L_6_C
3   output_dir: ./data
4   experiment_type: ML Classification
5   subjects_or_events: subjects
6   deployment_method: Singularity with Slurm
7   random_seed: 42
8   config_name: config_F-test_L_6_C_39-10-2025-1826.yaml
9
10 data_input:
11   groups:
12     alz:
13       - /path/to/sub-001/eeg/sub-001_task-eyesclosed_eeg.set
14       # ... (up to sub-036)
15     cntrl:
16       - /path/to/sub-037/eeg/sub-037_task-eyesclosed_eeg.set
17       # ... (up to sub-065)
18   reuse_processed_subjects: 'Yes'
19   save_processed_subjects: 'Yes'
20
21 preprocessing:
22   bands:
23     Delta: [0.5, 4]
24     Theta: [4, 8]
25     Alpha: [8, 12]
26     Beta: [12, 30]
27   window_size: 3.0
28   sliding_window: 0.5
29   normalize_psd: 'Yes'
30   epoch_rejection:
31     reject: 600.0
32     flat: 0.3
33
34 feature_extraction:
35   method: welch
36   features:
37     per_channel_across_bands: [band_power]
38     per_channel_per_band: [relative_band_power]
39
40 feature_transformation:
41   transformations:
42     - Univariate F-test
43     - MinMax scaler
44   f_test_selection_mode: fwe
45   f_test_selection_threshold: 0.05
46
47 data_transformation_strategy:
48   strategy: LPSO (Leave-P-Subjects-Out) - systematic cross-validation
49   lpso_subjects_per_group: 6
50   uneven_handling: wrap_around
51
52 pyspark:
53   master: 12
54   driver_memory: 8
55   executor_memory: 6
56
57 ray:
58   search_strategies:
59     - grid_search
60   grid_search:
61     models:
62       - XGBoost
63       - MLP (Neural Network)
64       - KNN
65       - SVM
```

Listing 1: Example YAML Config: Univariate F-test (F-test_L_6_C)

Naming note (consolidated). Paper-facing identifiers use the `F-test_` alias for the univariate feature-selection pipeline. In the implementation, this stage is built with PySpark's `UnivariateFeatureSelector`, which supports multiple univariate score functions (chi-squared, ANOVA F-test, and F-value) and selects the scoring rule from the configured feature/label types. In our AD/CN setting with continuous EEG

features, this corresponds to an ANOVA-style F-test branch of the selector. Some repository artifacts may therefore still contain legacy ANOVA_ strings from earlier pipeline naming. When present, they refer to the same F-test_ stage and not to a different method.

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